

The Role of Self-Concept and Social Support on Resilience in College Students Who Experienced Body Shaming

Nadia Wulandari

*Faculty of Psychology, University of Gunadarma
nadiawdr16@gmail.com*

Abstract

Body shaming or humiliating other people by offending their bodies is often thrown in jokes in social circles, both in the real world and in cyberspace. This study aims to examine the effect of self-concept and social support on the resilience of students who experienced body shaming. Respondents in this study were 210 people with the criteria for students aged 18-25 years who experienced body shaming. The results of the study using multiple regression techniques show that self-concept and social support simultaneously have a very significant effect on the resilience of students who experienced body shaming, with a large influence of 36.1% with a greater contribution given by social support then followed by self-concept to resilience.

Keywords: *Body shaming, resilience, social support, self-concept*

Body shaming often occurs everywhere in everyday life. Body shaming or embarrassing other people by insulting their bodies is often expressed in jokes with friends. Even though the aim is to joke or to get the listener to start healthy habits, in fact this actually has a negative effect. A study states that body shaming can make victims hate themselves and even continue their eating patterns to extreme points so that they become increasingly unhealthy. Not only that, depression and suicidal tendencies can also arise as a result of body shaming (Wisnubrata, 2020).

This body shaming treatment also often occurs among students and has several negative effects on individuals. In particular, individuals who experience body shaming have a low self-image, or perceive

themselves negatively. Apart from that, other effects that occur include feeling a lot of shortcomings, low self-esteem, shame, lack of self-confidence and anxiety. However, there are also some students who feel this is normal and consider it just a joke (Hidayat, Malfasari & Herniyanti, 2019).

Body shaming should not happen to anyone. But unfortunately, there are beauty standards that if someone does not meet them, they will have to endure harsh criticism of their appearance. In fact, more than half of Indonesian women (62.2%) admit to having been victims of body shaming during their lives. Of this number, almost half (47.0%) experienced body shaming with the main reason being that their body was considered too full. After that, 36.4% of women experienced body

shaming because of acne-prone skin. Of the remainder, as many as 28.1% experienced it because of a chubby face shape, as many as 42.6% experienced it due to acne-prone skin, as many as 23.3% experienced it due to dark skin color and as many as 19.6% experienced it due to a thin body (ZAP Beauty Index, 2020).

Apart from that, body shaming behavior can also be categorized as bullying behavior. Not a few people who do body shaming think of it as just a joke. In fact, this behavior can cause individuals who experience it to experience bad impacts, including mental health problems. For example, anorexia, binge eating disorder or even depression (Handayani, 2020).

To deal with this behavior, a person can instill a resilient or tough character to remain mentally strong. Resilience makes individuals not give up quickly when they encounter difficulties, believe in themselves, and are also creative in finding solutions (Laraspati, 2019). Resilience is defined as a process of good adaptation in facing difficulties, trauma, sad events, threats, or things that might trigger stress (Sippel, Pietrzak, Charney, Mayes & Southwick, 2015). Increasing resilience is one way to reduce the effects of bullying behavior on victims (Narayanan & Betts, 2014). Despite experiencing bullying, resilient individuals show lower levels of depression than non-resilient individuals (Sapouna & Wolke, 2013). Resilience can also be a factor that

supports an individual's level of satisfaction and acceptance of their body (Izydorczyk & Sitnik-Warchulska, 2018).

Social support can make individuals feel loved, liked, appreciated and valued, thereby enabling individuals to face unpleasant events in their lives (Bilgin & Tass, 2018). Social support is also known as the main environmental resource that encourages adaptive positive changes in crises and transitions that occur in an individual's life (Wolff & Sanchez, 2019). Individuals who receive social support can be more resilient than individuals who do not receive social support from their social environment (Sambu, 2015). The higher the social support an individual receives or feels, the higher the individual's resilience (Hidayat & Nurhayati, 2019).

One other thing that has an important role in the development of resilience in an individual is self-concept (Martins & Neto, 2016). Self-concept can be understood as an individual's overall idea of who he is physically, emotionally, socially, and in terms of other aspects that make up an individual's self (Ackerman, 2020). Individuals who are able to build social relationships and also have a positive self-concept can more easily develop resilience within themselves (Mota & Matos, 2015). An individual's resilience can trigger happiness and balance, and this is related to a high self-concept (Mota & Matos, 2015).

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Based on the background explained above, researchers can formulate research questions as follows, does self-concept influence resilience, does social support influence resilience, and do self-concept and social support jointly influence resilience in students who experience body shaming.

RESEARCH METHODS

Participants

Participants in this research were 210 students aged 18 to 25 years who experienced body shaming. Participants for this research were reached using an online questionnaire within a period of 20 days starting from 8 November 2020 to 28 November 2020. The online questionnaire distributed included sections on informed consent, identity, several additional questions related to the research, as well as the scale of each variable in this research.

The majority of participants in this research were female students with a total of 178 people (84%) and the remainder were male students with a total of 32 people (15%). Then, the majority of participants were currently studying at Strata 1 (N=170; 80%), followed sequentially by Diploma 3 (N=16; 7%), Strata 2 (N=11; 5%), Diploma 1 (N =9; 4%), Diploma 2 (N=3; 1%), and Strata 3 (N=1; 0.4%).

Measuring Instrument

Resilience. The measuring instrument used for the resilience variable in this research is The Connor-Davidson Resilience Scale (2003). The response categories used in this scale range from very inappropriate to very suitable with a score range of 1-4. An example of an item in this measuring tool is "I am able to adapt to change." This scale consists of 25 favorable items with a reliability of 0.89.

Social support. The measuring instrument used for the social support variable in this study was adapted from Liu and Chui (2014). The response categories used in this scale range from very inappropriate to very suitable with a score range of 1-4. An example of an item in this measuring tool is "there is a special person who is always there when I need him." This scale consists of 12 favorable items with a reliability of 0.89.

Self-concept. The measuring instrument used for the self-concept variable in this research was adapted from Veiga and Leite (2016). The response categories used in this scale range from very inappropriate to very suitable with a score range of 1-4. An example of an item in this measuring tool is "I often feel beautiful/handsome." This scale consists of 30 items, each of which consists of 11 favorable items and 19 unfavorable items with a reliability of 0.87.

Data Analysis Technique

The data analysis technique used in this research is multiple linear regression using IBM SPSS version 19.00 for Windows.

RESULTS

In Table 1 you can find information about the body shaming treatment of participants. First, the frequency with which participants experienced body shaming was the most

frequently reported by participants, followed by often and very often. Second, it can be seen how participants usually receive body shaming treatment from other people. The body shaming treatment that is most often mentioned is using verbal methods, then after that it involves physical touch, and then the last one is through social media.

Table 1. Information About Body Shaming Treatment for Participants

Category	Amount	Percentage
Frequency of experiencing body shaming		
Sometimes	110	52%
Often	73	34%
Very often	27	12%
Body shaming treatment received		
Verbal	203	96%
Involves physical touch	169	80%
In social media	40	19%
Perpetrators of body shaming		
Friends or relatives	183	87%
Family members	127	60%
Neighbors	68	32%
Spouse or ex	40	19%
Teachers	1	0,4%
Body shaming comments		
Too fat	93	44%
Too thin	73	34%
Related to the face	34	16%
Related to the height	34	16%
Related to skin color	19	9%
Related to hair	8	3%
Response when receiving body shaming treatment		
Silent/smiling but feeling hurt	113	53%
Laughing/joking	109	51%
Express your dislike for this treatment	32	15%
Just be sincere	3	0,1%
Actions after receiving body shaming treatment		
Trying to change the body	169	80%
Not trying to change anything	40	19%

Third, who are the perpetrators of body shaming towards participants? The perpetrators most often mentioned are friends or relatives, followed by family. Next, fourth, namely the various body shaming comments received by participants. The most frequently received comment was too fat, and the second most frequently received was too thin. Furthermore, the fifth data shows the description of the responses given by

participants when receiving body shaming treatment. The most frequent response is to remain silent or just smile even though you feel hurt, and this is followed by a response of laughing or being taken as a joke. Finally, the sixth is the participants' actions after receiving body shaming treatment. Trying to change the body is more of an action than not trying to change anything.

Table 2. The Influence of Each Variable on Resilience

Variable	B	Std. Error	β	t	Sig
(Constant)	1,150	0,170		6,764	0,000
Social support	0,556	0,078	0,453	7,158	0,000
Self-concept	0,161	0,044	0,234	3,699	0,000

Table 3. The Influence of Two Variables on Resilience

Variable	R	R Square	F	Sig
Social support and self-concept	0,601	0,361	58,470	0,000

It is known that the direction of the relationship between the three variables in this study is positive. Thus, the higher an individual's self-concept and social support, the higher his or her resilience. Meanwhile, the relationship between variables in this study has a value of $R=0.601$, which means the relationship is not close. It can be seen that self-concept has a very significant effect on resilience with a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). Likewise, social support also has a very significant effect on resilience with a

significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$). The results of the multiple regression test of self-concept and social support on resilience obtained a value of $F = 58.470$ and a significance value of 0.000 ($p < 0.01$), which means that self-concept and social support simultaneously have a very significant effect on resilience. The greater contribution is made by social support, followed by self-concept towards resilience. Apart from that, it was also found that the determinant coefficient (R Square) was 0.361 or 36.1%, which means

that the influence of self-concept and social support on resilience was 36.1% and 63.9% was influenced by other factors that could not be explained. in this research.

DISCUSSION

Both women and men are likely to experience body shaming, but this research found that women experience body shaming more than men. This may be because women find it easier to appreciate subjective experiences than men (Simoes, Ferreira, & Mendes, 2016).

The most frequently reported body shaming treatment was from friends, followed by family. This can have an impact on the individual regarding the way the individual views himself or what is called self-concept. This self-concept is formed from oneself, and also includes family, peers and social media (Fitriyah & Rokhmawan, 2019). The mother figure is also the source of messages or comments about the body that are most remembered from childhood. The meaning that individuals perceive regarding these comments is related to body image satisfaction and self-esteem. Comments that are interpreted positively are related to body image satisfaction and higher self-esteem (Rubinsky, Hosek, & Hudak, 2018).

The most frequently reported method of body shaming is through direct verbal treatment, followed by involving physical touch and then through social media. Bullying behavior verbally, physically and in the way of social relations due to a person's weight or physical condition can worsen the psychological mental condition, thoughts and feelings of the victim (Fitriyah & Rokhmawan, 2019).

Research conducted on students found that the comments from other people about their bodies that were most remembered from childhood included body size (e.g. fat or thin), body shape (e.g. tall or short), and certain body parts (e.g. hair, nose, or feet) and several others (Rubinsky, Hosek, & Hudak, 2018).

The research results showed that participants who had a positive self-concept and high levels of social support had higher levels of resilience. Thus, the research results presented above show that the research hypothesis, namely that self-concept and social support influence resilience, can be accepted.

Social support makes a greater contribution to the formation of resilience in individuals. This is because the social support felt by an individual can influence how the individual views the problem (Thoits, 2011). The presence of social support from a warm and supportive environment can build positive

emotions that are useful for individuals to face challenges and stress (Stewart & Yuen, 2011). Individuals who receive social support from family and friends tend to be more resilient than individuals who do not receive similar support (Donellan, Bennet & Soulsby, 2016). Thus, social support can influence and predict the level of resilience. The higher the social support obtained, the higher the individual's resilience (Hidayat & Nurhayati, 2019).

Furthermore, self-concept also has an influence on resilience. This is because individuals who have a negative self-concept, when they receive body shaming treatment, will take seriously other people who make embarrassing comments regarding being too fat or thin, thus making the individual feel insecure, embarrassed and not wanting to eat (Hidayat, Malfasari, & Herniyanti, 2019). Individual resilience as a trigger for happiness and balance is also related to a high self-concept (Mota & Matos, 2015). An individual's self-concept plays an important role in the development of self-resilience (Martins & Neto, 2016). These results are in line with research by Rachmawati and Listiyandini (2014) that individuals who have a positive self-concept have high levels of resilience. The development of individual resilience can be influenced by internal factors such

as self-esteem, self-efficacy and acceptance. As well as external factors such as parental involvement, high expectations, positive friendship groups and closeness to people in their environment (Hinduja & Patchin, 2017).

CONCLUSION

There are several important findings in this research. First, body shaming can occur in both women and men, but is dominated by women. Second, the most common form of body shaming is related to being too fat or too thin. Third, self-concept and social support jointly influence resilience in students who experience body shaming with a greater influence exerted by self-concept and then followed by social support on resilience.

SUGGESTION

The limitation of this research is that researchers cannot reach other variables that might influence resilience. This can be taken into consideration for further research to examine what other variables can influence resilience in students who experience body shaming.

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